

Bronsted Acid catalysed Hydrolysis of *N-p*-Chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic Acid

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The kinetics of the Bronsted acid catalysed hydrolysis of *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid have been measured in hydrochloric and perchloric acids in 20% (v/v) dioxane. On the basis of Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen, Yates-McClelland, Cox-Yates excess acidity treatments, the mechanism is seen as involving a pre-equilibrium protonation followed by a slow A-2 type nucleophilic attack by water. Temperature, salt and solvent isotope effects have also been probed.

The kinetic study of hydrolysis of hydroxamic acid has lagged until quite recently. Considerable efforts have been made towards the development of therapeutic agents in drug delivery systems¹. These compounds play vital role in iron-solubilisation and transport² and in selective DNA cleavage³. Acid-base equilibria and hydrolytic stabilities of these compounds are known to have an important bearing on their general usefulness in many biochemical and analytical applications. It is our plan to study hydrolysis of C- and N-substituted hydroxamic acids⁴. Herein we report the hydrolysis of *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid (Cl.C₆H₄N(OH)(C=O)(C₆H₅)) in an extensive range of HCl and HClO₄ at temperatures 45, 55 and 65° in 20% (v/v) dioxane medium. This substrate is also interesting in view of its potential utility in extraction processes and analytical procedures.

Results and Discussion

The rates of hydrolysis were determined spectrophotometrically by following the decrease in the characteristic absorption (520 nm) of the hydroxamic acid-ferric chloride complex. The reaction showed pseudo-first order kinetics. Formation of the products, i.e. benzoic acid and *p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine was identified qualitatively. The kinetic data along with other relevant information are assembled in Table 1. In perchloric acid, the pseudo-first order rate constant increases initially with acid concentration and reaches maximum and then drops with further increase in acid concentration. In hydrochloric acid no rate maximum was observed in the range of acidity examined.

Activation parameters were also determined for some acid solutions (Table 2). These values are fairly typical for A-2 reactions. Of interest is the variation of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger with acid concentration. Thus, while ΔH^\ddagger progressively increased as the acid medium became more concentrated, ΔS^\ddagger changed from a large negative value to less negative values, the overall effect resulting in little variation in ΔG^\ddagger . This implies that a change from a more to a less restricted transition state is occurring as the acidity is increased (or as $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is decreased).

TABLE 1-KINETIC DATA FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF *N-p*-Cl-PBHA IN 20% (v/v) DIOXANE WITH HCl AND HClO₄ AT 55°

[Acid] <i>M</i>	10 ⁵ <i>k_w</i> (s ⁻¹)	
	HCl	HClO ₄
0.75	2.55	2.51
1.45	3.92	5.33
1.93	4.07	6.25
1.93 ^a	9.82 ^a	—
2.9	4.72	7.92
3.5	15.30	8.01
4.5	17.00	8.64
5.0	23.0	9.68
5.0 ^a	28.94 ^a	—
5.8	31.04	14.39
6.5	32.86	9.17
7.5	35.20	6.75
9.0	39.54	—

^aDCl in D₂O.

Rate acidity correlations : The kinetics have been analysed by means of Bunnett⁵ ω and ω^* [2], Bunnett-Olsen⁶ ϕ , Yates-McClelland⁷ r , Bunnett-Olsen LFER treatments and the Cox-Yates excess acidity treatment⁸. The pK_{SH^+} value of *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid is -2.29 taken from earlier studies⁹. All the correlations are summarised in Table 3. The values covering as wide a range, imply that water has some additional role in the rate-determining step as well as that of nucleophile.

The value of r obtained by Yates-McClelland hydration treatment is close to 2, which gives the number of water molecules involved in forming the transition state. Recently, the Cox-Yates excess acidity method⁸ has proved to be of considerable value in determining the details of the mechanisms of reactions in strongly acidic media. Previously we applied this method for hydroxamic acids and showed that this method is a valid criterion for the mechanism of hydroxamic acid hydrolysis. A general expression (eqn. 1) for the Cox-Yates excess acidity treatment, have been derived for A-2 reactions on the basis of mechanism (Scheme 1),

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF *N-p*-Cl-PBHA*

Concn. <i>M</i>	Temp. °C	HCl					HClO ₄				
		<i>k_w</i> × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	<i>E_a</i>	Δ <i>H</i> [‡]	Δ <i>S</i> [‡]	Δ <i>G</i> [‡]	<i>k_w</i> × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	<i>E_a</i>	Δ <i>H</i> [‡]	Δ <i>S</i> [‡]	Δ <i>G</i> [‡]
0.75	45	1.75					1.91				
	55	2.55	42.4	29.2	-213	102.7	2.51	53.3	49.6	-181	103.4
	65	4.87					6.18				
3.5	45	5.53					3.72				
	55	15.3	73.6	71.6	-102	101.8	8.01	59.7	57.5	-150	102.0
	65	29.0					14.24				
5.8	45	11.36					5.24				
	55	31.04	83.5	81.1	-66	100.7	14.39	77.8	75.6	-90	102.2
	65	73.91					30.11				

**E_a*, Δ*H*[‡], Δ*G*[‡], in kJ mol⁻¹; Δ*S*[‡] in JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

TABLE 3—SUMMARY OF RATE ACIDITY CORRELATIONS

Correlation		HCl			HClO ₄		
		Acid range <i>M</i>	Slope	<i>r</i>	Acid range <i>M</i>	Slope	<i>r</i>
Bunnett ω	(log <i>k_w</i> + <i>H_A</i>) vs log <i>a</i> _{H₂O}	6.75–9.0	3.63	0.995	0.75–4.5	5.11	0.968
Bunnett ω*	[log <i>k_w</i> - log [H ⁺]] vs log <i>a</i> _{H₂O}	0.75–35	5.43	0.969	1.45–5.0	1.89	0.986
Bunnett-Olsen φ	(log <i>k_w</i> + <i>H_A</i>) vs (<i>H_A</i> + log [H ⁺])	0.75–9.0	0.93	0.995	0.75–5.8	1.08	0.987
Yates-McClelland <i>r</i>	[log <i>k_w</i> - log <i>h_a</i> /(<i>h_a</i> + <i>K_{SH+}</i>)] vs log <i>a</i> _{H₂O}	3.5–6.5	2.39	0.976	3.5–7.5	2.09	0.978
Bunnett-Olsen LFER	[log <i>k_w</i> - log <i>h_a</i> /(<i>h_a</i> + <i>K_{SH+}</i>)] vs (<i>H_A</i> + log [H ⁺])	0.75–7.5	0.61	0.994	0.75–6.5	0.32	0.984
Cox-Yates <i>m</i> ₂ [‡] <i>m</i> [*]	[log <i>k_w</i> - log [H ⁺]] - 2 log <i>a</i> _{H₂O}] vs <i>X</i>	3.5–9.0	0.65	0.940	0.75–5.8	0.54	0.898

$$\log k_w - \log C_{H^+} - 2 \log a_{H_2O} = \log k/K_{SH^+} + m_2^* m^* X \quad (1)$$

A diagnostic feature of the A-2 mechanism is that a plot of left-hand-side of equation (1) vs *X* (excess acidity) should give a straight-line with slope value of 0.6 or less. The plots obtained are shown in Fig. 1. The slope values are given in Table 3, which is indicative of A-2 mechanism.

Salt-effect : Many added salts increase the protonating power of the medium and therefore generally assist acid hydrolysis. Bunton *et al.*¹⁰ showed that the salt-effect of perchlorates is negligible or slightly negative in A-2 acid-catalysed ester hydrolysis, whereas chlorides assist the hydrolysis slightly. In the present studies, the chloride assists the hydrolysis and perchlorate slightly depresses the hydrolysis rate. Thus, the data suggest that the substrate is undergoing reaction by A-2 pathway, involving transition states which are strongly hydrogen-bonded to water. There-

fore, it will be favoured by acids having anions of higher charge density (Cl⁻). It seems probable that perchlorate ion, a large ion of low charge density, stabilises carbonium ion like transition state.

Kinetic solvent isotope effect : The solvent effects (*k_D*/*k_H*) of (1.93 *M* HCl = 2.41) and (5.0 *M* HCl = 1.25) (Table 1) are consistent with a reaction involving a pre-equilibrium protonation at lower acidities followed by a rate-determining nucleophilic attack of D₂O or H₂O. D₃O⁺ is a considerably stronger acid in D₂O than H₃O⁺ is in H₂O; the fast pre-equilibrium will therefore be shifted to the right in the deuterated solvents, producing a greater concentration of the protonated species which is the reactant in the slow step of the reaction.

The available evidence suggest that the hydrolysis proceeds via an A-2 mechanism in which a rate-determining attack of water to the carbonyl carbon, leads to the transition complex and subsequent hydrolysis giving the products.

Experimental

N-p-Chlorophenylhydroxamic acid was prepared according to literature procedure¹¹. The acids used were of A.R. grade. Dioxane (B.D.H., A.R.) was used.

Fig. 1. Excess acidity plots for the A-2 mechanism of hydrolysis of *N-p*-Cl-PBHA at 55°C (●) HCl and (○) HClO₄

Kinetic measurements were made by the spectrophotometric method described previously⁴. Least-square analysis was carried out on a Wipro SX-386 personal computer under MS-DOS.

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